

Wetlands and Wildlife For the Future: The Clemson University James C. Kennedy Waterfowl and Wetlands Conservation Center

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Wetlands in the United States have declined by more than half since European colonization, and losses continue to climb. Wetlands have long been viewed as waste areas that impede agriculture and development, mainly leading to this decline. However, wetlands' values and ecosystem services have been quantified in recent decades, increasing wetland conservation efforts. Wetland restoration to increase waterfowl and other wetland-dependent wildlife is now commonplace. Moreover, federal policies requiring wetland mitigation to compensate for wetland losses are in place to conserve wetland ecosystems (Strager et al. 2011, Becker et al. 2022). Restored and mitigated wetlands can provide habitat for numerous species (Balcombe et al. 2005, Strain et al. 2014,

Millikin et al. 2019) and essential ecosystem services (Gingerich and Anderson 2011, Gingerich et al. 2014, 2015). However, the recent Sackett versus U.S. EPA decision weakens wetland protection for some isolated wetlands (Supreme Court of the United States 2023).

Waterfowl are among North America's most highly regulated huntable group of species. Their migrations across multiple countries, states, and provinces require cooperation among numerous jurisdictions (U.S Fish and Wildlife Service 2023). Waterfowl, particularly dabbling ducks and geese, have been studied extensively. However, new challenges posed by climate change, habitat loss, diseases, changes in human behavior, and other factors provide

fodder for continued waterfowl research. Moreover, the advent of new technologies in combination with modern statistical modeling offer opportunities for contemporary research at scales previously untenable. Holistic waterfowl and wetland conservation also require that research on other wetland-dependent wildlife be conducted.

The James C. Kennedy Waterfowl and Wetlands Conservation Center at Clemson University was launched in 2014 to address many of the pressing issues noted above. Mr. James C. Kennedy, an ardent wetland and waterfowl conservationist, endowed the Center at Clemson University. He also established similar programs at Mississippi State University, the University of Wisconsin-Stevens Point, and Colorado State University. The Clemson University Kennedy Center is housed at the Belle W. Baruch Institute of Coastal Ecology and Forest Science

on the 6,500-ha Hobcaw Barony in Georgetown, South Carolina (Fig. 1).

The Kennedy Center aims to *lead in science and education to sustain waterfowl and wetlands of South Atlantic Coastal Ecosystems (and other wetland ecosystems) and train future waterfowl and wetland ecologists and managers*. The Kennedy Center achieves this by recruiting highly qualified and motivated undergraduate, master, and doctorate students to study wetlands, waterfowl, and other wetland-dependent wildlife (Fig. 2). The Center also builds partnerships with researchers, managers, biologists, and others to address and solve contemporary wetland management issues. The complexity of modern-day management and research challenges necessitates diverse collaborations to ensure appropriate funding and expertise are available. The Kennedy Center fosters such collaborative efforts.

Current projects at the Clemson University James C. Kennedy Waterfowl and Wetlands Conservation Center address 1) the role of artificial nest boxes for wood duck (*Aix sponsa*) recruitment (Fig. 4), 2) the use of natural tree cavities by nesting wood ducks, 3) waterbird habitat use and migration chronology, 4) interaction among alligator (*Alligator mississippiensis*) diets, microplastics, and other contaminants in wetlands, 5) ecology and management of banana water lilies (*Nymphaea Mexicana*), 6) integration of eastern oysters (*Crassostrea virginica*) into saltmarsh restoration, and 7) use of drones to study waterbird use of historic breached and unbreached ricefields (Fig. 3), 8) human dimension related to management of historic rice fields, 9) American crocodile (*Crocodylus acutus*) ecology and management, and 10) greenhouse gas dynamics in coastal wetlands. Past projects include 1) evaluating management strategies for submerged aquatic vegetation and invertebrates, 2) black-bellied whistling

duck (*Dendrocygna autumnalis*) and wood duck reproduction in nest boxes, 3) evaluating aerial surveys to monitor waterbirds, 4) human dimensions of an online waterfowl course and waterfowl researchers, 5) microbial communities in wood duck nest boxes, and 6) predation in wood duck nest boxes.

In addition to Clemson students conducting research through the Kennedy Center, we also have a Graduate Student Partners Program for students external to Clemson. The Partners Program expands collaborations and allows other students to benefit from the Kennedy Center's time, talent, or resources. The benefits of being in the Graduate Student Partners Program include the potential for exchanging ideas, sharing research equipment, receiving financial support, and collaborating on grants, papers, and other products.

Clemson University's James C. Kennedy Waterfowl and Wetland Conservation Center serves as a training ground for

future wetland and waterfowl managers and biologists and as a creator of original scientific research. The number and amount of external grants and contracts obtained by the Center, the number of graduate students supported, and the number of collaborators continues to grow. The future of wetlands, waterfowl, and other wetland-dependent wildlife will be in good hands due to continued training and research from the Kennedy Center and similar centers across the globe.

However, there are not enough centers focused on these aspects. I encourage universities, government organizations, and others to continue collaborating and expanding opportunities for conducting original research and providing quality educational programming for wetland and waterfowl enthusiasts. Please check out our [webpage](#) or visit us on [Facebook](#) for more information on the James C. Kennedy Waterfowl and Wetland Conservation Center.

Fig.1 James C. Kennedy Waterfowl and Wetlands Conservation Center staff and students are stationed at the Belle W. Baruch Institute of Coastal Ecology and Forest Science in Georgetown, South Carolina, USA.

Fig.2 Blair Abernathy, James C. Kennedy Undergraduate Scholarship Recipient and summer intern at the James C. Kennedy Waterfowl and Wetlands Conservation Center.

Fig.3 James C. Kennedy Waterfowl and Wetlands Conservation Center Ph.D. student Akshit Suthar, with his poster explaining his research on drones and waterbirds at one of many outreach and education events.

Fig.4 Research Technician Nick Makarewicz is placing a web-tagged wood duck (*Aix sponsa*) duckling back in its nest box.

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About the Author

Dr. James T. (Jim) Anderson is the James C. Kennedy Endowed Professor of Waterfowl and Wetland Ecology, the Director of the James C. Kennedy Waterfowl and Wetland Center, and a faculty member in the Department of Forestry and Environmental Conservation at Clemson University. Before Clemson, he was a Wildlife and Fisheries Resources Professor and the Davis-Michael Professor of Forestry and Natural Resources at West Virginia University. He received his B.Sc. in Wildlife from the University of Wisconsin-Stevens Point, his M.Sc. in Range and Wildlife management through the Caesar Kleberg Wildlife Research Institute at Texas A&M University-Kingsville, and his Ph.D. in Wildlife Science from Texas Tech University. Dr. Anderson's research centers on wetlands, riparian systems, and wetland-dependent wildlife ecology. He has over 30 years of experience conducting wetland and wildlife research, published >180 scientific articles, mentored >60 graduate students, and garnered over \$29 million in research grants and contracts.